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Review Article

Caesalpinia Bonducella: A Pharmacognostic And Pharmacological Overview

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ABSTRACT

Within the Caesalpiniaceae family, *Caesalpinia bonducella* (L.) Fleming (Syn. *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb, Syn. *Caesalpinia crista* Linn.) is a prickly shrub that is found all over the world, but is most commonly found in tropical regions of India, Sri Lanka, and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. The plant is a very significant medicinal plant that is used in traditional medicine since all portions of it have therapeutic qualities. Anxiolytic, antinociceptive, antidiarrheal, antidiabetic, adaptogenic, anthelmintic, antiestrogenic, anti-inflammatory, antimalarial, antimicrobial, antifungal, antispasmodic, antioxidant, antiproliferative, antipsoriatic, antitumor, larvacidal, muscle contractile, hepatoprotective, anticonvulsant, and antifilarial properties have all been reported associated with the plant. Alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, and triterpenoids have all been found in *Caesalpinia bonducella* seeds according to phytochemical study.

INTRODUCTION

The use of medicinal plants as a possible source of therapeutic help has grown in importance in the global health system for both people and animals, not only in cases of illness but also as a resource for preserving good health. Nonetheless, it is important to understand which components of the medicinal plant are in charge of its therapeutic effects. Consequently, in order to employ it therapeutically, it becomes necessary to extract, isolate, and identify the phytoconstituent in

question. Solvents are primarily used in the extraction of plant drugs. Traditionally, extraction techniques such as maceration, percolation, digestion, decoction, and hot continuous extraction have been employed. Worldwide interest in plant research has grown recently, and a substantial amount of data has accumulated to demonstrate the enormous potential of medicinal plants utilized in a variety of traditional systems. The public's interest in the usage of herbal

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treatments is growing at the moment. Moreover, plant extract was the source of many western pharmaceuticals. Numerous herbs are mostly utilized to treat conditions related to the central nervous system, liver, digestive system, and metabolism. They can be helpful as a medication or supplement in the treatment or management of a variety of disorders due to their ability to have a substantial therapeutic impact. The biological activity of herbal medicines, medicinal plants, and their extracts and isolated substances have been shown to be diverse. These have been and still are used as dietary supplements or folk medicine for a variety of illnesses. Belonging to the Fabaceae / caesalpiaceae family, *Caesalpinia bonducella* (L.) Fleming (Syn. *Caesalpinia bonduc* (L.) Roxb, Syn. *Caesalpinia crista* Linn.) is a prickly shrub that is widely distributed throughout the world, particularly in India, Sri Lanka, and the Andaman and Nicobar Islands. It is particularly found in tropical regions of India [1&2]. The plant is a highly useful medicinal plant that is used in traditional medicine since all portions of it have therapeutic qualities [3]. There have been reports of the plant's antifilarial, antinociceptive, antidiarrheal, and anxiolytic properties. The presence of alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, tannins, and triterpenoids has been identified by phytochemical examination of *Caesalpinia bonducella* seeds [4–5].

PHARMACOGNOSTIC STUDY

A large climber, its branches downy and delicately gray, and it is covered in strong yellow prickles that are both hooked and straight. The stipules are a pair of reduced pinnae at the base of the leaf, each with a long mucronate point. The leaves are bipinnate, 30–60 cm long, and have short, thorny petioles. There are seven pairs of pinnae, and between each pair on the underside are three to eight pairs of leaflets with one or two tiny recurved prickles. has two hooked stipulary spines at the base, each about 5.0–7.5 cm in length. Leaflets: 6–9 pairs, membranous, elliptic to oblong, obtuse, strongly mucronate, glabrous above and somewhat puberulous below; dimensions: 2.0–3.8 cm × 1.3–2.2 cm. Flowers have long peduncles and dense terminal racemes, generally spicate, with supraaxillary racemes that are 15–25 cm long and closely spaced at the top. Bracts are squarrose, linear, acute, and up to 1 cm long. The pedicels are extremely short in the buds and elongate to 5 mm in flowers and 8 mm in fruits. They are brown and fluffy. The calyx is fulvous, hairy, and measures 6 to 8 mm. The lobes are obovate-oblong and obtuse. Petals are yellow and oblanceolate, with declinate filaments that are flattened at the base and long, silky white hairs covering them. Pods were short-stalked, rectangular, and were 5.0–7.5 by around 4.5 cm. They were heavily armed with wiry prickles. The 1-2 oblong, green, up to 1.3 cm long, glossy, firm seeds eventually become gray. They serve as a medium for jewelry. [6,7, 9, 10, 11]

Figure 1: *C. bonducella* plant

Figure 2: *C. bonducella* seed

SYNONYMS [7, 8,12]

Hindi name- Sagar Gota ,Kantkarej, Kantikaranja,.

English name- Nicker seed, nicker nut, bonduc nut, and fever nut

Persian name- Khayahe-i-iblas

Sanskrit name- Kantakikaranja, Kantakini, Karanja, Krakachika, Kuberaksah, Kuberakshi, Kuberaksi, Latakaranja, Prakiriya, Prakirnah, Putikah, Putikaranja, Putikaranjah, Putikaranji, Tinagachhika, Tirini, Valli, Varini, Vitapakaranja

Urdu name- Akitmakit.

Telgu Name: Gaccakayai Mulluthige.

Tamil Name: Kazharchikkaai, Kalachikai, Kalichikai, Kazarci, Kalarci ver, Kalarcik Koluntu, Kalarcip paruppu, Kazharchikkaai.

Kannada name- Gajjiga, Kiri gejjuga, Gajikekayi.

Malayalam name- Ban-karetti, Kaka-moullou, Kazhanji, Kalanci, and Kajanchikkur .

TAXONOMIC CLASSIFICATION

Kingdom : Plantae

Phylum : Magnoliophyta

Division : Magnoliopsida

Class : Angiospermae

Order : Fabales

Family : Fabaceae / Caesalpiniaceae

Genus : Caesalpinia

Species : bonducella

PHARMACOLOGICAL STUDIES

Numerous research investigations on pharmaceuticals were spurred by the presence of diverse phytochemicals in different regions of the plant. However, there are currently insufficient studies and records available about the plant. A plethora of undiscovered phytochemicals with enormous potential to herald new directions and methods in the field of clinical treatments may become apparent with more thorough scientific research. Table No. 1 illustrates how several scientific literature have described the plant's sections as having important characteristics.

Table 1: Pharmacological Studies Of Seeds, Leaves And Flowers

S.NO.	Plant part	Uses	References
1	Seeds	Anti-inflammatory	13
2	Seeds	Antimicrobial	14
3	All parts	Immunomodulator	15
4	Seeds	Hypoglycemic and antidiabetic	16
5	Flowers	Analgesic	17
6	Leaves	Antioxidative stress	18
7	Seeds	Antidepressant	19
8	Seeds	Antipyretic	20
9	Seeds	Antiasthmatic	21
10	Leaves	Hepatoprotective	22
11	Young twigs and leaves	Anticancer	23
12	Leaves	Antifeedant	24
13	Seeds	Antidiabetic	25
14	Seeds	Antibacterial and cytotoxic effects	26
15	Leaves	Nephroprotective	27
16	Seeds	Hypolipidemic	28
17	Seeds	Antiallergic and antihistaminic actions	29
18	Seeds	Antifertility	30
19	Leaves	Antiproliferative and pro-apoptotic	31
20	Leaves	Anthelmintic	32
21	Seeds	Antiulcer	33
22	Seeds	Antimycobacterial Activity	34
23	Seeds	Anticataract	35

24	Leaves	Antidiarrhoeal	36
25	Seeds	Antifilaria	37
26	Leaves	Muscle contractile activity	38
27	Leaves	Antifungal and Antispasmodic	39
28	Seeds	Anti-estrogenic activity	40
29	Seeds	Antidiuretic	41
30	Leaves	Antitumor	42
31	Seeds	Anxiolytic	43
32	Seeds	anticonvulsant	44

CONCLUSION

C. bonducella is a widely spread shrub with deep roots that is evergreen with a firm, woody stem. This plant's leaves are glossy, ovate-shaped, compound elliptical, and placed alternately on either side of the branches. Several beneficial phytochemicals have been extracted from various sections of this plant, including the seeds, which include caesalpin, β -caesalpin, and α -caesalpin, terpenoids, and neutral saponin. Biosterols such as sitosterol, heptacosane noncrystalline, bitter glycoside, bonducin, and neutral saponin are found in kernels; leaves contain pinitol, glucose, calcium, and brazzillin; homoisoflavonoids, 6-Omethylcaesalpinianone, and caesalpinianone are found in bark; roots elaborate cassane furanoditerpene, caesalpinin, bonducellpins A, B, C, D, and diosgenin are found in the roots. These strong, unique phytochemicals exhibit a variety of pharmacological characteristics. The research has reaffirmed that *C. bonducella* has a variety of active metabolites in different regions that may be used to treat various illnesses. Also, it has been noted that due to the existence of distinct bioactive metabolites, various plant sections exhibit varying pharmacological actions. However, in order to fully investigate all of the opportunities and possibilities the rich plant presents, further scientific study and documentation are needed. This review compiles the data from current pharmacological research studies. The plant exhibited antidiabetic, antioxidant, antihyperlipidemic, antispasmodic,

immunomodulator, and antibacterial properties in its seeds, bark, and roots. *C. bonducella*'s flowers have analgesic properties. The leaves of *C. bonducella* have anti-tumor, anti-ulcer, and antifilarial properties, while the seed kernels have antimalarial properties. There is still need for more investigation even though the plant has a wealth of powerful compounds that make it medicinally rich. This wild plant is abundant in biomarker compounds of medicinal interest and has been demonstrated to have several pharmacological actions; nevertheless, research is still needed to produce formulations for various illnesses and disorders, which might lead to an increase in the plant's economic worth in the future.

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